

ACCEPTABILITY OF CASHLESS ECONOMY AFTER DEMONETIZATION IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Demonetization is the act of stripping a currency unit of its status as legal tender. Demonetisation is necessary whenever there is a change of national currency. The old unit of currency must be retired and replaced with a new currency unit.

November the 8th, 2016 - the date has become a landmark for the Indian economy. It was an ordinary day for any Indian, but then the clock struck 8:15 p.m. and there was our Prime Minister addressing the countrymen. In a 25-minute long speech, the Prime Minister had waged a war against black money by withdrawing legal tender character of Rupees 500 and Rupees 1000 notes with effect from midnight, and issuing new Rupees 500 and Rupees 2000 in place.

The surging menace of fake currency, especially in high denomination, cannot be stressed enough. This in turn, is hoarded as black money, and is misused by terrorists for anti-national and illegal activities. India is still known as a cash-based economy.

Keywords: *Demonetization, Black Money, cashless transactions, GDP.*

DATA COLLECTION

The paper is based on the secondary data. The secondary data was collected from various published sources like reports, magazines, journals, newspapers and the like

Needs of demonetization:

1. To eliminate black money from the markets
2. To Stop terror funding
3. To Reduce corruption
4. To Eject the counterfeit currency out of the system

The cashless transactions take place through digital currencies like digital payment channels like mobile wallets. In a truly cashless society, legal tender i.e. money is exchanged and recorded only in the electronic and digital forms.

Such a scenario is widely considered to be hypothetical as most experts believe that some physical currency will always stay in circulation. Therefore, the meaning of cashless economy in popular usage is an economy where transactions in cash are minimal and not necessarily nil. So the more appropriate term would be- ‘less cash’ society.

Cash is king but its throne is being toppled; and few countries are leading the way. The table below shows the top ten cashless countries on basis of value of non-cash transaction:

Rank	Country	Non-cash payments' share of total value of consumer payments (Percentage)
1	Belgium	93
2	France	92
3	Canada	90
4	United Kingdom	89

(Figures: worldatlas.com)

Here, the percentage of cash transactions on basis of value in Belgium is 7%, in Canada it is 8% in Canada it is 10% and in UK it is 11%. In India, this figure is almost 96% but it is reducing day-by-day.

Keywords: *digital currencies, cashless transactions, cash transactions.*

The Need of Cash less Economy

It’s been nearly 300 years since paper money became accepted as legal tender. While much has changed about how we make, sell, and buy goods, cash has stuck around.

So why are we trying to get rid of it now?

The most prominent reason is that cash trails are hard to trace, leaving doors open for frauds, corruption and burglary. As cash permits anonymity in transactions, it leaves the door open for tax evasion and even terrorist funding.

Another reason is the high cost of handling cash not only in terms of money but also in terms of time.

RBI and commercial banks in India spend Rs 22,000 Crores annually in this regard. A study for Harvard Business Review gave the following figure-“New Delhi’s 11 million inhabitants collectively spend some 72 million hours per year chasing cash.”

(Figures: lesscash.in)

It is not only India- almost the whole of the Indian subcontinent suffers from high cost of handling cash.

Lot of cash in circulation also allows hoarding and black money. There is a popular saying-“If you want to eliminate black money, eliminate money.”

All these reasons make a compelling case in favour of migration towards a cashless economy.

- **The Success Story So Far:-**

Despite the pain caused, demonetisation appears to be promising at its face value. The scheme brings in some much needed reforms for the economy. Here is how it can bring about a revolutionary change-

- ✓ All the cash deposited in bank accounts, is generating data that is being used by the Income Tax Department for mapping transactions. As a result, the Income Tax Department has carried out 586 searches across the country and seized ` 300crores cash, and caught unaccounted income of ` 2600 crores, as reported by The Economic Times on 16th December, 2016.
- ✓ It is apparent that the tax net is set to widen and the government expects to record a major cash inflow in terms of cash and penalties in FY 2017. If that happens, it will have a positive impact on fiscal deficit also.
- ✓ The sudden move has hit the illegal activities like terrorist financing, atleast in the short- term.
- ✓ It has also been said that the new ` 500 and ` 2,000 notes are less susceptible to being faked, as they have advanced security features- implying that it will be nearly impossible for counterfeit notes to creep into the markets.
- ✓ Although the GDP growth rate has declined in the short-term, restrictions on cash economy and increase in government revenue are expected to improve the GDP in the long run.
- ✓ Demonetisation has lowered down the inflation, much to the relief of the common man. Till the markets are infused with enough liquidity, the prices are expected to remain flat for a long time.
- ✓ More assesseees and tax-evaders are expected to come within the tax net, further widening the tax base.
- ✓ The government had promised to take steps against black money, and it has done just that. The move has instilled a sense of confidence towards the government among the people, and therefore, they are willing to co-operate, despite the hardships.

It seems impossible for demonetisation to scoop out black money completely. It is because those who receive it the illicit way do not keep it in cash-form for long. It is either converted to investments in precious metals like gold, or in real estate or stashed away in countries considered to be tax havens. Demonetisation will hardly make any difference to them.

Impact of Demonetization on Indian Economy:

1) Black Money and Corruption

By demonetization, Black money will be taken out of Indian system. As predicted by ICICI Securities Primary Dealership the government's plan to remove INR 500 and INR 1,000 notes from circulation will disclose up to INR 4.6 lakh crore in black money. Corruption will also be automatically reduced by removing black money from economy.

2) Funding

Funding for smuggling and terrorism will take a blow since all the money will get back to bank and from there it is easy to identify the fake currency. Demonetization thus affects the funding of terror networks in Jammu and Kashmir, North-eastern states and the other areas

3) Real estate

Another impact of the demonetization would be reduction in cash transactions in real estate. This is likely to reduce to real estate prices and make it affordable. In the short term, prices of real estate would come down for the same reason above. There will be fewer suitcases moving.

4) Elections

Demonetization has shocked political parties. Many states like Punjab and Uttar Pradesh.

5) Gold/Silver and Jewellery

After demonetization the demand for gold and other precious metals rise greatly. Because people are trying to invest their black money in gold to make it white in short period. But demand for gems and jewellery to decline in the next two to three quarters.

6) Digital payments

People adopting online payments system such as Paytm etc. after ban for high denomination currency in India. Digital transaction systems, E wallets and apps, online transactions using E banking, usage of Plastic money (Debit and Credit Cards), etc. will definitely see substantial increases in demand. This behavioural change could be a game changer for India in the near future.

7) Fake Currency

The impact on the fake currency would be more significant. Many dealers with the existing counterfeit notes would be trapped as they would have to take the notes to the bank and have better chances of getting their racket exposed. Thus, they have only option to destroy their notes and incur losses.

8) GDP

The sudden decline in money supply and increase in bank deposits is going to adversely impact consumption demand in the economy in the short term. This, coupled with the adverse impact on real estate and informal sectors may lead to lowering of GDP growth.

9) Markets

There will be positive move in markets in long run that could bring confidence of overseas investors in Indian stock markets. Market goes a bit down in the short and medium term. India is still a very attractive destination on a long term basis. It is not the best market in the next three months.

10) Decease in Interest Rates

We will see a lowering interest rates for education loans, home loans and medical loans very soon. It will make higher education and medical facilities more accessible. This change is hard to undo because if any subsequent government increases loan it will suffer huge backlash.

11) Lower Inflation

As the black money goes out of the system the money supply will shrink to some degree. This will reduce inflation rate in the absence of any open market interventions by the Reserve Bank of India.

Recent Developments -

Soon after the announcement of the scheme, the government had proposed a ‘window’ for those who want to declare their unaccounted income post closure of Income Declaration Scheme on 30th September.

The government notified the Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Deposit Scheme, 2016 on 16th December, 2016 to be effective from 17th December and remain open till 31st March, 2017, for people to declare their undisclosed income and escape prosecution. Here are the key features of the scheme-

- ✓ Any person can make a declaration of income in respect of cash or deposits in his account.
- ✓ This undisclosed income will be chargeable at the rate of 30%. This amount of tax will be increased by a surcharge at the rate of 33%, called the Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Cess. In addition, the declarant shall be liable to pay a penalty of 10%. Therefore, the tax, surcharge and penalty sums up to around 50% of the total undisclosed income.
- ✓ No deduction of any expenditure, or set-off of losses will be allowed.
- ✓ The declarant shall set aside an amount equal to 25% of the undisclosed income as a non-interest bearing deposit, which will be refundable after four years from the date of deposit.
- ✓ The payment of tax, surcharge, penalty, and the deposit should be made before filing the declaration, which shall be accompanied with the proof of payment and the proof of deposit.
- ✓ The amount so declared will not be includible in the income of any assessment year.
- ✓ The tax, surcharge and penalty so paid will be nonrefundable.

The Challenges of Cashless Economy

This means there are two major economies within the national economy- Rural and Urban. Even though consumers in the metros are increasingly using credit and debit cards for commercial transactions, things outside the metros leave much to be desired. The rural areas are still not an integral part of the financial or digital mainstream.

Whether it is the corner shop or consumer electronics showroom, an apparel store or a hospital, transactions in small towns are still in cash. In the metros, too, cash transactions are hugely popular in malls. In a study of retail stores in malls, management consulting firm A.T. Kearney discovered that only 10% of the sale by value happened via cards; 90% took place in cash. (Figures: livemint.com)

Most consumers buying luxury brands at luxury malls or outside also make cash payments. Most of the jewelry is also purchased in cash. Even e-Commerce brands allow CoD (Cash on delivery) to attract more customers.

In such a situation, to be able to become less dependent on cash, the rural economy needs to undergo a mammoth transformation. This can be a major hurdle as people in the small towns and villages are usually resistant and skeptical when faced with adoption of new technologies. They are financially less literate when compared to the people from the cities and fear being charged more if they use cards for transactions. Sometimes, people have bank accounts but these accounts end up lying un-operational. There is also the issue of connectivity. Many villages, mostly those in remote areas, are yet to be electrified. People in many villages and small towns do not own mobile handsets even today. Many of them do not have internet connections. And even if there is connection, the networks are weak and unreliable in numerous places.

Also being an economy dominated by small retailers and proprietors, the businessmen may not have the willingness to invest in electronic payment infrastructure.

To sum up- to be able to go cashless, educating the masses and making the general public aware of the benefits of going digital has to be given utmost importance and attention.

The Benefits of Cashless

The benefits of a cashless economy are numerous.

To begin, transparency will increase manifold.

When every transaction is routed through the digital payment channels, a permanent trail will be available and this will mean reduced scope for tax evasion, black money, corruption and hoarding. This will also deliver a huge blow to criminal and terrorist activities.

With less physical cash and black money in circulation, real estate prices will decline leading to a boom in the infrastructure industry.

As tax evasion reduces, the governments will have more money to spend on social and public welfare schemes. Since these payments too will be done digitally, the beneficiaries will conveniently and directly receive their dues

The cost of keeping cash in circulation will reduce and lead to more funds for the banks and the governments.

The velocity of transactions will increase multiple times leading to more number of transactions in a small period of time. For example, the same amount of money can be circulated throughout the country any number of times through digital payment systems. A buyer in Mumbai will pay the seller in Bengaluru who will pay the dealer in Hyderabad and so on. This will lead to increase in GDP and the country's economy will grow and develop by leaps and bounds.

Fake notes and Counterfeit notes will no longer have harmful effects on the economy.

Each of these benefits will have a domino effect and this chain will lead to a robust and healthy economy.

The Disadvantages of Cashless

As the old adage goes “Every coin has two sides”, a less cash economy too is not without demerits.

An example is that of Sweden. The number of bank robberies in Sweden plunged from 110 in 2008 to 16 in 2011 because most Swedish banks simply don't handle cash anymore but in the past decade the cases of electronic fraud have more than doubled. (Figures: totalpayments.org; theguardian.com)

Some of Sweden's neighbors, in response to EU's increasing regulations on restricting cash usage, are demanding a “constitutional right to pay in cash” fueled by concerns around negative interest rates and a perceived loss of privacy that comes with digital money.

There are growing concerns about the ability of public agencies to look through digital records. Paper money, they feel, provides them anonymity and freedom from traceability, both of which are qualities that digital payments do not offer.

Cash has stubbornly resisted going the way of digital extinction. Paper currency is ubiquitous. For many users, cash equates to a sense of security as it is almost always universally acceptable and for many it is a sense of independence from government oversight.

Old people's organizations also fear that those who prefer cash, out of reluctance to use new technology or simply because they find it easier to keep track of their spending, will be disadvantaged, while educators worry that young people will be tempted to spend money they do not have.

It may surprise you that there are countries which are going opposite to the tide. Germany is one such country where usage of cash is still very popular.

Although there are disadvantages, the benefits far outweigh them.

EXAMPLES OF STEPS TAKEN TOWARDS CASHLESS ECONOMY

Few examples of steps taken in various SAFA countries towards reducing dependence on cash bKash is a specialized company in Bangladesh focused on mass market mobile financial services. Launched in July 2011, bKash reached 11 million accounts by the end of 2013, just 30 months after launch. In India, Finance Ministry along with the National Payments Corporation of India (NPCI) and Reserve Bank of India (RBI) is bringing about various initiatives like UPI (Unified Payment Interface) to usher in a cashless economy Haryana, a state in India, has begun training the government officials who in turn will educate the general public about digital transactions. Many banks have conducted camps to impart information about the same. Government offices are also being equipped with PoS (Point of Sale) machines. Prizes have also been announced for those who proactively participate in this movement. Sri Lanka Interbank Payment System (SLIPS) is an online interbank electronic fund transfer system catering mainly for low-value payments in Sri Lanka , I would like to quote the example of South Korea.

Starting out as a very cash dependent society, the Korean government has successfully put into place policies to encourage cashless behaviour. For example, South Korea introduced a preferential VAT treatment for consumers who pay with cards, moving the share of cash from 40 per cent to 25 percent within four years from 2002 to 2006. (Figures: totalpayments.org)

All the member countries of SAFA have the basic infrastructure and the logistics needed to begin the journey towards an economy with minimum cash. All that is needed is the first step and I can proudly say that almost all member countries have already taken this first step. Therefore it can be safely concluded that the possibility of cashless economy in SAFA countries is high.

Feasibility of the same however will depend on the execution and the implementation of the policies and programs. If everyone is involved in the processes and Incentivization of cashless transactions is adopted, the idea of a less cash economy is definitely feasible in the SAFA countries.

CONCLUSION

Overall, Demonetisation is a good move. We should support Demonetisation, but keep reminding the government to iron out the execution issues. Given the extent of black money in the country, and the tiny taxpayer base, something had to be done. It had to be drastic. It has been done now. We should now do what it takes to make it succeed.

The advantages are much dominating and it will be in the long term interest of our country comfortably outweighing the disadvantages. Government needs to take all the necessary steps so as to ensure that there will be a smooth flow of currency exchanges. It would turn into chaos if government takes no necessary steps to circulate money correctly. It will make a massive change in our economy. We congratulate the entire government and those hidden brains of our democracy that brought this decision. I hope the above helps to understand Demonetisation better. We should focus on making the exercise work, which means supporting the idea and yet demanding better execution.

Finally, to conclude about acceptability, I believe I speak on behalf of all the citizens of all member countries when I say that if a step makes our country better, we will accept it with open arms and support it whole-heartedly. Inconveniences and hardships are but small prices to pay for the growth of our country. We are all ‘kisans’ and ‘jawans’ of our countries and this is the least that we can do for our motherland.

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